

The Role of the Teacher's Methodological Skills in Forming Students' Idea Generation Skills

Rustamov Nazir Chorievich¹

¹ National Institute of Educational Pedagogy named after Kori Niyazi 1st stage foundation doctoral student

Abstract:

In this article, it is considered one of the important tasks for the education system today, self-confident, able to communicate effectively, with an intuitive way of thinking, creative thinking and research abilities are developed, flexible to different situations, able to work in a team. An opinion was expressed about the important tasks facing the education system in educating and bringing up young people who can show and generate new ideas.

Keywords: development, creativity, pedagogue, generation of ideas, professional skill, methodology, science and technology.

One of the important factors in the development of creativity among students is to ensure their cognitive activity in the process of individual-oriented learning. In recent years, one of the important demands of the society is the formation of individuals who are self-confident, able to communicate effectively, have an intuitive way of thinking, have developed perception and research skills, are flexible, can work in a team, and generate new ideas. For this, the need to develop personal qualities and creative thinking in students corresponding to such skills in the educational system is increasing. In the traditional education process, not enough attention was paid to the formation of such qualities and skills in students. Because the traditional teaching system is based on the direct transfer of knowledge from the teacher to the student. Most students acquire knowledge, but teachers do not use the necessary pedagogical measures to develop the skills of using this knowledge in non-standard situations. For this, they lack methodological skills. At the same time, as a result of not acquiring the necessary knowledge, it is observed that students' competitiveness and idea generation skills are not sufficiently formed.

Searching for highly qualified teachers and developing their professional skills to the required level has always been considered one of the main issues of the education system. It is clear from the research that today the system of providing knowledge to students needs to be radically changed. For this, the development of professional skills of future teachers and teachers is of particular importance. The national program aimed at the development of school education requires the creation of an innovative system of providing the necessary knowledge to socialize students, ensure their competitiveness, and have the ability to generate new ideas. Because of the current conditions of advanced science and technology, the need for specialists with the ability to create and apply new technologies is increasing. For this, it is necessary to arm students with innovative ideas.

Today, there are a number of trends related to the development of the educational process. They are:

1. To prepare students for life in rapidly changing conditions in the educational process in connection with the development of science and technology, to form motivations for learning in them throughout their life.
2. To transition to an informed society, to have opportunities to expand intercultural relations, and to develop students' communicative and informational competences.
3. To democratize the educational environment in general secondary education schools, to prepare students for the life of civil society, to achieve their responsible and conscious choice, to form the skills of being able to get out of the selection situations without being influenced by various pressures.
4. It is observed that the dynamic development and diversification of the economy, the growth of competition, the reduction of unskilled and low-skilled labor sectors, and the dynamic-structural changes in the field of employment require the development of students' creativity and the ability to choose a targeted profession.

One of the important issues facing the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to expand the scope of innovative teaching. This, in turn, requires the teacher to have methodological skills. It is important to consider the development of students' idea generation skills when introducing mechanisms for continuous improvement of the quality of education. For this, it is necessary to pay special attention to the development of thinking ability in them. It is important to discover the ability to think, create news, and achieve concrete results in order to form the skills of generation of ideas in students. In the process of teaching subjects, teachers should pay attention to the development of students' activity of generating new ideas. Generating ideas is a universal and timeless skill. One of the main tasks of the educational system is the formation of intellectual entrepreneurship motives in students. Such motives increase students' desire to acquire new knowledge. Today, the following problems facing the educational system of Uzbekistan await their solution:

1. There is an increasing need for teachers to develop such qualities as methodical skills, dedication to their work, a responsible approach to fulfilling obligations, high professional qualifications, and erudition.
2. Enrichment of educational programs is required in order to systematically present knowledge about art and culture in the educational process.
3. For the purpose of developing students' thinking, such as setting difficult tasks in front of them.

Today, there is a special need to determine the role of the family in educating students and developing their skills of generation of ideas, thinking, and worldview. In the educational process, students are provided with more theoretical knowledge of academic subjects. Very little time is devoted to the development of their empirical skills and creative abilities, and in the family, parents

do not always pay attention to the new ideas born in students. Stimulating and supporting their interests is the basis for the birth of new ideas. Students are more inclined to generate new ideas, especially during adolescence. Parents and teachers realize this in time and support them, creating a basis for the birth of new ideas.

It is also important to develop intellectual entrepreneurship among students based on social requirements. This requires a special methodical skill from the teacher. To date, teachers hardly use the method of regressive analysis of new ideas born in students. Such an analysis requires the use of mechanisms for the development of creative thinking in students. It is important to develop students' creative thinking in the educational process in order to develop the ability to generate ideas. First of all, it is necessary to develop an open mind in students. Thinking and making judgments ensure that students find the right solutions to problems. For this, it is necessary to create an environment of self-control and effective thinking in students. Socrates also tried to develop creative thinking skills in students, not just imparting knowledge.

The development of active thinking skills is formed with the help of methods of performing creative tasks. It is important for teachers to know these methods well and be able to use them in every lesson. Because creative thinking and critical thinking activities are closely related to each other. In this process, it is necessary to rely on the four important rules of thinking put forward by R. Descartes. They are:

1. Refrain from making hasty decisions; perceive things that are clearly expressed in the mind; and do not give rise to doubts.
2. Dividing identified difficulties into parts that are easy to solve.
3. To control the flow of one's thoughts, to strive to learn step by step from the simplest, easy-to-know things to complex events.
4. Explain your point fully to make sure nothing is left out.

According to Descartes, thinking is not formed only on the basis of knowledge. It requires thoughtful analysis and consideration of various options leading to a solution to the problem. It can be seen that the main source of students' ability to generate ideas is the development of creative thinking. For this, first of all, teachers should acquire methodological skills related to the development of creative thinking in students.

List of used literature:

1. Safarova R.G. Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda prognozlash kompetensiyasini shakllantirishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10675669>.
2. R.G.Safarova. Kognitiv pedagogikaga oid nazariy yondashuvlar. Monografiya. – Toshkent: "Science and innovation" nashriyoti, 2024. – 186 bet.
3. Ibraimov X., Quronov M. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). – T., "Sahhof", 2023.
4. Samiyev Sh.X., Narzullayeva F.F. Kreativ fikrlash. Darslik. Buxoro. 2022-yil.
5. Ponomarev Ya.A. Ijodiy fikrlash psixologiyasi. M: Gumanitar tadqiqotlar instituti, 2001-yil.
6. Pedagogika: ensiklopediya / tuzuvchilar: Jamoa. – Toshkent: "O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi" Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2015.
7. Xotamov I.S., Olimov M.K. Kreativ fikrlash. Innovatsion rivojlanish nashriyot matbaa uyi. Toshkent, 2021-yil.
8. Narzullayeva G.S. Kreativ fikrlash. O'quv qo'llanma. "Durdon" nashriyoti. Buxoro, 2022.
9. Po'latova D., Ro'zmatova G.M. G'arb falsafasi tarixi.—T.: "Fan va Texnologiya", 2018.
10. Saidg'aniyeva S.Y., Abdullayeva Sh.R., Abduqunduzov I.A. Kreativlik pedagogik faoliyatni rivojlantirishning asosiy omili sifatida. Scientific progress. Volume 1. Issue 4.